

THE CYANINE DYES OF THE PYRIDINE SERIES. PART II.

BY M. Q. DOJA AND DEANUSHDHAR PRASAD.

p-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde has been condensed respectively with α -picoline-methoiodide, -ethoiodide, -propyl iodide and-butyl iodide; and the chemical, dyeing and photographic properties of the compounds thus produced examined, with a view to investigating the influence of change of structure on the properties of these dyestuffs, specially their sensitising power.

In view of the great importance of 2-*p*-dimethylaminostyrylpyridine alkyl halides (I),

as sensitisers, the influence of the change of anion (*cf.* Kiprianov and Schusser, *Proc. Charcow State Univ.*, 1936, 4, 49) on the chemical, optical, and photographic properties of the methoiodide of (I), was examined by one of us and reported in previous communications (Doja, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940 17, 347; 1941, 18, 281). Whereas in those communications X was varied and Y kept unchanged, in the work to be described hereafter, X, the anion, has been kept unchanged (iodide), and Y has been successively replaced by methyl, ethyl, propyl, and butyl, and the properties of the dyes, thus produced, have been examined (*cf.* Mills and Pope, *Photograph. J.*, 1920, 40, 191; Hamer, Heilbron, Reade and Walls, *J. Chem. Soc.* 1932, 251). All these dyestuffs were prepared by the condensation of the appropriate quaternary iodide of α -picoline, prepared by slight modifications of the methods of Murril (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1899, 21, 828), with *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde in presence of piperidine (*cf.* Barbier, *Bull. Soc. Chim.*, 1920, 28, 427; König and Treichel, *J. pr. Chem.*, 1921, 102, 63; Mills and Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2736; Mills and Raper, *ibid.*, 1925, 2466). They are highly coloured, lustrous, crystalline compounds, showing characteristic reflexes. When examined under a polarising microscope, they exhibit pleochroism, light of one colour being transmitted in one orientation of the polariser, and another colour in an orientation at right angles thereto. These properties of the crystals,

together with their melting points, which show an increase of about 10 degrees as we descend the series, are given in Table I.

TABLE I.

Name.	M.p.	Shape.	Colour by reflected light.	Colour through transmitted light.	Reflex.	Pleochroism.	
						Colour of light in one position of polariser.	Colour after rotation through 90°
(B)	274°	Needles	Vermilion red	Claret red	Blue	Yellowish red	Nearly opaque
(C)	265°	Rectangular plates	Reddish violet	Orange	Reddish blue	Reddish yellow	Orange-red
(D)	255-56°	Rhombs	Maroon	Orange-red	Greenish blue	Reddish yellow	Dull red
(E)	245°	Laminated plates	Amethyst	Deep orange red	Strong blue-green	Golden red	Opaque nearly

Being true cyanine dyes, they exhibit the general characteristics of this class of compounds. They are soluble in alcohol and water and insoluble in non-ionising solvents like ether and benzene. The solubility in alcohol and water decreases with increasing molecular weight, the butyl iodide being the least soluble among the four. The solution of these dyestuffs is decolorised by mineral acids and the colour restored by treatment with alkalis.

Aqueous and alcoholic solutions of those compounds are orange-yellow in colour, the yellow component increasing with dilution. The relative intensities of the colour of solutions of these dyes have been determined colorimetrically and the results are shown in Table II. It is interesting to note that there is no regular increase or decrease in colour intensity in the series, the ethiodide forming relatively the most intensely coloured solution.

TABLE II.

Relative intensity	Depth of the solution of			
	(B).	(C).	(D).	(E).
15	11'5	11'4	19'2	20'3
			19'3	
	11'5	19'6	11'46	19'3
			31'0	
24	19'7	19'8	19'70	30'6
			30'5	
	1'31	1'22	0'78	0'74
			0'79	

The aqueous solution of these compounds dyes silk, cotton and wool in varying shades of orange-yellow, the reddish tinge of which increases with ascent in the series (Table III). Both neutral and acid solutions have been used, and in each case the same gradation in colour is noticed. The best colour is produced on wool which can be dyed any colour ranging from light lemon-yellow, to deep orange-red by varying the amount of acid added to the dye-bath. These colours, however, are not fast either to soap washing or to sunlight. In the case of washing of silk, it has been observed that the fastness increases as we ascend the series. It has been further noted that wool on exposure to sunlight loses its colour much more slowly than either silk or cotton.

TABLE III.

Name.	Colour produced on			Remarks.
	Cotton.	Silk.	Wool.	
(B)	Yellow-orange	Bright orange-yellow	Yellow-orange	1. For cotton and wool both neutral and acid baths were used, the latter always giving a weaker tint than the former.
(C)	Deep yellow-orange	Bright yellow orange	Orange	2. For silk only weakly acid baths were used.
(D)	Orange	Bright orange	Orange (reddish tinge)	3. The increase in reddish tinge with ascent in the series is most prominent in wool.
(E)	Deep orange	Bright orange (reddish tinge)	Red-orange	

TABLE IV.

Name.	Total range of sensitisation.	Range of uniformly intense sensitisation.	Sensitisation.	
			Minimum.	Maximum.
(B)	4250-6100 Å	4450-5400 Å	5050 Å	5300 Å
(C)	4250-6000	4400-5400	5000	5250
(D)	4250-5750	4450-5200	5000	5200
(E)	4200-6200	4350-5750	5050	5400

In Tables I-IV, B, C, D, E refer respectively to the methoicdide, ethoicdide, propyl iodide and butyl iodide of the dye.

We acknowledge with pleasure our indebtedness to the Government of Bihar for the grant of a research scholarship to one of us (D. P.). Our thanks are also due to Professor L. M. Chatterjee of the Physics Department for valuable help in taking the sensitisation spectra.

FIG. 1.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Pleochroism.—These were determined by means of a Radial Research Microscope, fitted with a polariser.

The sensitisation spectra of these dyes together with that of an unbathed plate is given in Fig. 1. It will be seen that the butyl iodide shows an uniformly intense band from about λ 4350 to λ 5750. The short gap in the blue-green region, which frequently occurs with sensitisers for the red and yellow region of the spectrum, is not found in this substance. Bearing in mind the comparative ease with which this compound can be obtained in the pure state, we regard it as a better sensitiser for this region than the German product "Pinaflavol". For commercial purposes therefore, we have named *2-p*-dimethylaminostyrylpyridine-butyl iodide, "Sensitin Z". The methyl and the ethyl compounds give nearly similar spectra, and the propyl compound produces a definitely poorer induced sensitisation. The salient features of the sensitisation spectra of these compounds are shown in Table IV.

Colorimetry.—Duboscq colorimeter was used, the strength of the solution being 1g. of the dye in 250,000 c.c. of rectified spirit.

Dyeing.—Cotton, mordanted with tannic acid and fixed with tatar emetic, "scoured" silk, and carefully cleaned wool were used. The fastness tests were carried out according to the standard prescribed in Colour Index of the Society of Dyers and Colourists.

Sensitisation spectra were taken in the same way as described by Doja (*loc. cit.*), except that the reference scale was set up with the help of an Edser-Butler plate, the wave-lengths of the bands of which were determined by means of a grating spectrometer. The solutions used were 1:25,000 in rectified spirit, and the time of exposure was 3 minutes.

2-p-Dimethylaminostyrylpyridine-ethyl iodide.—*p*-Dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (5 g.), α -picoline ethiodide (2.99 g.), and piperidine (1 c.c.) were dissolved in absolute alcohol (67.5 c.c.) and the solution boiled under reflux for 10 hours. The deep orange solution on cooling deposited a red crystalline substance which was recrystallised from absolute methyl alcohol, yield 5.5 g. (75.3 %). (Found: N, 7.52, 7.58; I, 33.56, 33.58. $C_{17}H_{21}N_2I$ requires N, 7.37; I, 33.42 per cent).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyrylpyridine-propyl iodide.—A solution of α -picoline propyl iodide (4.5 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (7.84 g.), and piperidine (1 c.c.) in absolute alcohol (65 c.c.) was boiled under reflux for 6 hours. The orange-red solution was allowed to cool and the solid deposited was recrystallised from methyl alcohol, yield 5.4 g. (80.6%). (Found: N, 7.25, 7.31; I, 32.52, 32.32. $C_{18}H_{23}N_2I$ requires N, 7.11; I, 32.25 per cent).

2-p-Dimethylaminostyrylpyridine-butyl iodide.— α -Picoline butyl iodide (3.3 g.), *p*-dimethylaminobenzaldehyde (1.77 g.), absolute alcohol (35 c.c.) and piperidine (0.5 c.c.) were heated together to a brisk boil in a flask with a condenser. Crystals soon began to separate from the deep orange-red solution, but the heating was continued for 8 hours. The filtered dye was dried in a vacuum desiccator, and recrystallised from absolute methyl alcohol, yield 4.05 g. (84%). (Found: N, 7.01, 7.03; I, 31.07, 30.9. $C_{19}H_{25}N_2I$ requires N, 6.86; I, 31.12 per cent).